

Carbon tax salience counteracts price effects through moral licensing

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Carbon taxes raise the costs of carbon-intensive products to penalize their consumption. Policymakers can decide whether the carbon tax is hidden or indicated explicitly as a component of the retail price. This policy design decision has effects on demand that have been overlooked. Here we show that salient carbon taxes are less effective than hidden taxes in reducing demand because being aware of paying a carbon tax activates a moral licensing process that encourages consumption. Across four experimental studies and two pilot experiments, we found that participants' purchase intention was consistently higher when the carbon tax was salient. This effect remained robust with different products, carbon tax levels, and additional carbon footprint labels. Salient carbon taxes had a stronger effect on the purchase intention of the climate change concerned and less conservative individuals because they were more susceptible to a boost in moral self-concept triggered by paying the carbon tax.

Keywords: Carbon tax; tax salience; moral licensing; climate change; carbon pricing

1. Introduction

Increasing the price of carbon-intensive goods and services through a tax on carbon emissions is the preferred market-based climate change mitigation policy for many economists, environmental scientists, and politicians (Engström et al., 2020; Goulder and Parry, 2008). Primarily, carbon taxes are conceived as Pigouvian taxes to change behavior through internalizing negative externalities rather than raising revenue: Since internalizing the cost of externalities associated with carbon emissions increases production costs and consumer prices, carbon taxes promote low-carbon innovation and discourage carbon-intensive consumption (Aldy et al., 2010). Confronted with a price increase, buyers are expected to reduce the consumption of the taxed products. Carbon taxes are based on the assumption that individuals behave according to standard economic theory, with higher prices reducing demand for price-elastic products.

However, research in the environmental domain has provided numerous examples of behavior diverging from the standard economic model. For instance, carbon offsets for electricity use may reduce carbon emissions, but may even increase energy consumption for some individuals, leading to additional emissions (for an overview, see Truelove et al., 2014). Financial incentives encouraging low-carbon transportation can have a normative influence on consumer choice beyond price effects (Hilton et al., 2014). Also, behavioral responses to price increases caused by commodity taxes can vary depending on whether consumers are aware of paying a tax or not (Chetty et al., 2009). At the retail level, the carbon tax can either be not visible or separately stated and identified in the price (Partnership for Market Readiness, 2017). Showing the carbon tax amount as part of the product price is not mandatory, but there has been public pressure for transparency about the impact of carbon taxes on prices and their revenue use (Carattini et al., 2018; Klenert et al., 2018; Maestre-Andrés et al., 2019). However, awareness of paying a carbon tax could trigger a moral licensing process that interferes with its demand-reducing effect. Moral licensing refers to situations in which individuals can derive confidence for morally questionable actions from their past moral behavior (Jordan et al., 2011; Merritt et al., 2010; Monin and Miller, 2001; Mullen and Monin, 2016). Because paying a carbon tax can be construed by the individual as such a moral behavior, carbon taxes may be less effective in curbing carbon-intensive demand than expected by policymakers.

Underperforming carbon taxes (i.e., the price increase fails to reduce demand to the extent predicted by standard economic theory) could exacerbate delays in meeting climate targets (Bertram et al., 2015; Strefler et al., 2021). Policymakers and retailers need to gain more insight into this moral licensing effect to inform their decision of whether or not to make carbon taxes visible to consumers as part of the retail price.

The effect on consumer demand of a salient versus a hidden carbon tax, that is, an equal price increase not marked as a carbon tax, has not been studied so far. Nor has the demand for a product showing a carbon tax as part of the price been compared with that of an equally priced product not

indicating a carbon tax. To study the consumer demand effect of salient vs. hidden carbon taxes, the underlying moral licensing process, as well as moderating factors, we conducted two pilot studies and four US-representative survey experiments. Our research contributes with a novel effect and explanatory process to the ongoing debate on the effectiveness and adequateness of carbon pricing mechanisms (e.g., Hahnel et al., 2020; Lanz et al., 2018; Rivers and Schaufele, 2015; Mattauch et al., 2022; Panzone et al., 2021), and extends the scope of extant moral licensing theory (e.g., Jordan et al., 2011; Merritt et al., 2010; Monin and Miller, 2001; Mullen and Monin, 2016), in particular, concerning negative spillovers of proenvironmental behavior (Burger et al., 2022; Meijers et al., 2014; Noblet and McCoy, 2018; Werfel, 2017). Our findings have practical implications for climate policy design and respond to recent calls (Farhi and Gabaix, 2020; Mattauch et al., 2022) to develop emission-curving instruments that account for consumers' endogenous preferences.

2. Theoretical framework

2.1. The moral licensing effect of salient carbon taxes

Moral licensing refers to a psychological process that allows individuals to behave in a morally questionable way because they have previously engaged in morally desirable behavior. Such individuals may experience a boost in their moral self-concept because their moral behavior provides them with moral credits (Khan and Dhar, 2006). Thus, individuals are more likely to act immorally if a previous behavior has already secured their moral self-image (Jordan et al., 2011; Merritt et al., 2010; Monin and Miller, 2001; Mullen and Monin, 2016). An initial positive behavior can lead to a negative behavioral spillover that balances a prior good deed with a negative action (Dolan and Galizzi, 2015). Moral licensing is a special case of negative behavioral spillover (Truelove et al., 2014). Since the concept was first coined by Monin and Miller (2001), moral licensing has been widely reported (Blanken et al., 2015).

In the environmental domain, contributing to climate change mitigation has been shown to alleviate the moral obligation to behave pro-environmentally in the future (Meijers et al., 2014; Noblet and McCoy, 2018; Werfel, 2017). Individuals reminded of their past climate-friendly behavior show less motivation to reduce other climate-harmful behaviors in the future (Burger et al., 2022). Moral licensing could explain negative behavioral spillovers such as increases in carbon-intensive behavior after participating in a corporate carbon offset program (Günther et al., 2020). A particular case of moral licensing—prospective moral licensing (Cascio and Plant, 2015)—occurs when individuals minimize to themselves the negative consequences of their actions because they anticipate that their future good deeds will compensate them (Brown et al., 2011).

Carbon taxes can form part of the retail price implicitly and be hidden from the consumer, but they can also be made salient to the buyer as an explicit part of the price tag. Fearing an excessive and unfair tax burden, public opposition to carbon taxes has shaped policy design, demanding full transparency about the tax's impact on prices and its revenue use (Carattini et al., 2017; Savin et al., 2020). The majority of voters prefer governments to be transparent during the implementation process and to earmark carbon tax revenues to finance climate change mitigation projects (Carattini et al., 2018; Maestre-Andrés et al., 2021). Consequently, information provision and earmarking are present in many carbon tax schemes worldwide (World Bank, 2022). Transparent pricing implies informing consumers about the carbon tax amount they are paying when purchasing a product.

However, when carbon taxes are salient, consumers may not react as modeled to carbon pricing policies because the psychological mechanisms triggered by the monetary incentive will disrupt the price signal (Stoll and Mehling, 2021). Being aware of paying a carbon tax may alter consumers' purchase behavior (Hahnel et al., 2020; Mattauch et al., 2022; Panzone et al., 2021). Although a study has found that a visible carbon tax on gasoline can have a stronger demand curbing influence than market-driven price increases (Rivers and Schaufele, 2015), some evidence suggests the opposite. An experiment showed that, when the retail price included a visible carbon price, carbon

footprint information may be less likely to lead to the choice of a wine with a lower carbon footprint (Soregaroli et al., 2021). Also, monetary incentives designed to induce switching to grocery products with a lower carbon footprint can be less effective than neutrally framed price decreases of the same magnitude (Lanz et al., 2018).

When consumers are made aware that a higher product price is caused by a carbon tax, this price increase may not have the same effectiveness in reducing demand as price increases caused by market conditions. We expect that awareness of paying a carbon tax will trigger a moral licensing process which increases purchase likelihood. Consumers, who are aware they are paying a carbon tax, may interpret this additional payment as a moral act, which leads to a boost in moral self-concept, allowing them to consume carbon-intensive products without feeling immoral. Consumers will therefore be more likely to consume a product showing the carbon tax. As a result, the demand curbing effect of a salient carbon tax will be weaker than that of a mere price increase caused by a hidden carbon tax.

H1: Salient (vs. hidden) carbon taxes have a weaker consumer-demand-reducing effect.

H2: The effect of a salient (vs. hidden) carbon tax on consumer demand is mediated by an increase in moral self-concept.

2.2. The moderating effects of climate change concern and conservative political orientation

Despite growing evidence, it is yet unclear under which conditions moral licensing takes place (e.g. Blanken et al., 2014; Urban et al., 2019, 2021). Given that prior moral behavior seems a necessary but often not sufficient condition to trigger moral licensing, research has focused on the identification of moderators that facilitate or inhibit moral permission to behave unethically (Mullen and Monin, 2016). For example, concrete (vs. psychologically distant) and unambiguous (vs. ambiguous) prior behaviors are more likely to trigger moral licensing in subsequent behaviors (Brown et al., 2011; Conway and Peetz, 2012). The likelihood of moral licensing depends not only

on the characteristics of the initial behavior but also on the personal traits of the person undertaking the action. These include the importance individuals place on their actions as a sign of their identity (Meijers et al., 2019) and the perceived moral obligation to achieve their personal goals (Sussewind and Hoelzl, 2014).

Overall, individuals will tend more to moral licensing the stronger they are morally committed to addressing the problematic issue (i.e., climate change) that is the target of the behavior that allows them to license (Burger et al., 2022; Gholamzadehmir et al., 2019). Therefore, not all consumers will be equally susceptible to the influence of carbon tax salience because moral licensing will take place only when paying the carbon tax is regarded as a moral deed, and consuming despite carbon emissions a morally questionable act. This will likely be the case for consumers concerned about climate change, but not that of climate change skeptics. Since climate change concern is often linked to a less conservative political orientation (Czarnek et al., 2021; Gillis et al., 2021; Lacasse, 2015), less conservative individuals will also be more likely to license. Less climate-concerned and conservative-leaning individuals, however, may fail to see paying the carbon tax as a moral act and consuming the product as a climate harmful, morally questionable behavior.

H3: The effect of a salient (vs. hidden) carbon tax on consumer demand is moderated by a) climate change concern and b) conservative political orientation through the moderation of its effect on moral self-concept. The effect is stronger (weaker) for a) more (less) environmentally concerned and b) less (more) conservative consumers.

3. Overview of the studies

To test the effect of salient vs. hidden carbon taxes, the underlying processes, and boundary conditions, we conducted two pilot studies and four main survey experiments. The samples of the four main studies were representative of the US population in terms of gender, age, income, and education, and were recruited via the research panel provider Prolific. Participants were presented

with different products (a cell phone, microwave oven, TV, premium beef hamburgers, or sports shoes) and prices in realistic purchase scenarios, and their purchase intention was assessed on a five-point Likert scale measuring their likelihood to purchase the product. The demand-reducing effect of the salient carbon tax was tested by comparing the purchase intention between experimental groups.

In Pilot Study 1 (N = 200) we showed the effect of carbon tax salience on moral self-concept, as the first part of the moral licensing process with a convenience sample of university students. Pilot Study 2 (N = 400) addressed the second part of the moral licensing process, testing the effect of moral self-concept on purchase intention with an online sample drawn at random from the US panel of the Prolific survey platform. In Study 1 (N = 1500) the effect on consumer demand of a salient vs. hidden carbon tax was assessed in comparison to a baseline product price without the carbon tax. In Study 2 (N = 600), we additionally measured the effects on moral self-concept to confirm the moral licensing process. In Study 3 (N = 400) we addressed the influence of different carbon tax levels (5% and 15% price increases) to discern whether the salience effect of the carbon tax affected demand differently depending on its amount. Study 4 (N = 400) aimed to rule out the alternative explanation that demand increased due to the information carbon taxes were conveying about the environmental impact of the product. Study 4 furthermore replicated previous results in a simulated online shopping environment. In addition, all studies assessed the influence of participants' environmental concern and political orientation on the carbon tax salience effect.

Appendix A provides supplementary methodological information. Appendix B reports the pilot studies and complementary analyses. The complementary analyses reported in Appendix B refer to Study 1 (Supplementary Note 1), Study 2 (Supplementary Note 2), Study 3 (Supplementary Note 3), Study 4 (Supplementary Note 4), Pilot studies (Supplementary Note 5) and an internal meta-analysis (Supplementary Note 6). The complementary analyses of all the main studies consisted of manipulation checks, multiple regressions of the carbon tax salience effects on purchase intention

and logistic regressions of the carbon tax salience effects on purchase decision. Besides, mediation and moderated mediation analyses were conducted for Study 2.

We obtained ethical approval from the Ethics committee of (*University name and code number of the approval have been anonymized for peer review*) to conduct the survey experiments, complying with all relevant regulations for research with human participants. None of our studies involved deception. We reported all treatment conditions and measures included in the studies. The materials, pre-registrations, data and code for all studies conducted in this research project are available as an Open Science Framework (OSF) permanent archive at:

https://osf.io/fyuva/?view_only=9a6e3b0e35404ee08b9f27efd2739a5b.

4. Study 1: Consumer demand effects of salient vs. hidden carbon taxes

4.1. Method

4.1.1. Participants and procedure

We conducted Study 1 to compare the demand-reducing effect of a salient carbon tax with that of a hidden carbon tax. For the study we recruited a US representative sample of $N = 1,500$ individuals (52.13% female, $M_{\text{age}} = 43.30$, $SD_{\text{age}} = 14.55$; Table A.1 in Appendix A shows demographic details) through the Prolific survey platform (<https://prolific.co/>). In all studies, informed consent was obtained before participants completed an approximately 5-minute online Qualtrics survey. Participants received a monetary compensation depending on their completion time with a minimum of \$6.50 per hour. The sample was drawn at random from the Prolific online panel of US individuals, adjusting quotas for a representative sample of the US population in terms of age (18+), gender, income, and education.

Participants were assigned at random to one of three experimental groups of a between-groups experimental design (salient carbon tax vs. hidden carbon tax vs. baseline price without carbon tax). Each participant was presented at random with one out of five products: a cell phone, a microwave

oven, a LED TV, sports shoes, and or premium beef hamburgers. Respondents were prompted to imagine a shopping scenario in which they were considering the purchase of the product. In the baseline price condition, products were presented at their original price without the carbon tax. Participants in the salient carbon tax condition were informed that a carbon tax was included in the price, and that the carbon tax was a measure against climate change that had been introduced with the aim of lowering the carbon emissions generated during the manufacturing and transport of all products. They were shown a 15% increased price with the carbon tax amount indicated explicitly. Participants in the hidden carbon tax condition saw the same products with the 15% higher price, corresponding to an implicit carbon tax, of which they were not made aware.

The effectiveness of the carbon tax salience manipulation, that is, the awareness of paying a carbon tax, was confirmed in a separate manipulation check detailed in Appendix B (Supplementary Note 1). See Supplementary Methods in Appendix A for the materials used in all studies, products, and pricing. Study design, data collection method, hypotheses, and planned analyses were pre-registered on AsPredicted (<https://aspredicted.org/blind.php?x=3y577k>).

4.1.2. Measurement

Participants were asked to rate their *purchase intention* on a scale ranging from *very unlikely* = 1 to *very likely* = 5. As an additional robustness check, participants subsequently indicated their *purchase decision*; whether they would definitely buy the product (*no* = 0, *yes* = 1). We further measured participants' *climate change concern* (van der Linden, 2015) with four items using a 5-point Likert scale that ranged from *not concerned at all* = 1 to *very concerned* = 5, as well as how *acceptable* (*not acceptable* = 1 to *very acceptable* = 5) and *effective* (*not effective at all* = 1 to *very effective* = 5) they thought carbon taxes were (Steg et al., 2006). The questionnaire concluded with demographic questions, which included a political orientation question. In addition, in an open-ended question, participants were asked what they thought was the purpose of the survey (Khan and Dhar,

2006). None of the respondents guessed the purpose of the experiment. Table A.5 in Appendix A presents the scale items and the reliability of all measures.

4.2. Results

Study 1 showed that a 15% increased price reduced purchase intention significantly compared to the baseline price condition when the carbon tax was hidden ($\Delta PI = -0.27$, 95% CI (-0.43, -0.11), $t(1497) = -3.33$, $P = 0.001$). However, the same price increase did not reduce demand when consumers knew it was caused by a carbon tax ($\Delta PI = 0.04$, 95% CI (-0.12, 0.20), $t(1497) = 0.47$, $P = 0.646$); that is, purchase intention was not significantly different from the baseline price condition. A comparison of purchase intentions between the salient carbon tax and hidden carbon tax conditions showed that at the same 15% increased price, purchase intention was higher when the carbon tax was salient instead of hidden ($\Delta PI = 0.31$, 95% CI (0.14, 0.47), $t(1497) = 3.69$, $P < 0.001$). For this and all other statistical analyses, we report two-tailed test statistics with cluster-robust standard errors to adjust for the presence of heteroskedasticity and, in Studies 3 and 4, additionally to account for the nested data. Figure 1 shows the positive effect of carbon tax salience on purchase intention for Study 1 and also for Studies 2, 3 and 4, which provide consistent evidence of this effect. The mean values for individual products are presented in Figure 2. There was no evidence supporting an interaction between the effects of the experimental conditions and product type on purchase intention ($F(8, 1485) = 1.17$, $P = 0.32$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.01$).

In Study 1, we analyzed the effect on demand of the price increase caused by the salient vs. hidden carbon tax in comparison to the baseline demand at the original price. However, since the baseline condition is the same for both the salient and hidden carbon tax group, and because in both cases purchase intention is compared to the same purchase intention in the baseline group, the observed effect of carbon tax salience on consumer demand is the result of the difference in purchase intention between the salient vs. hidden tax conditions—independent of the baseline condition at the

price without the tax. Therefore, we excluded the baseline price condition from further analysis of Study 1 and focused on the salient carbon tax and hidden carbon tax groups, both at the increased price including the carbon tax, and conducted Studies 2, 3 and 4 without the baseline price condition.

Fig. 1. Purchase intention by experimental group.

P values in Study 1 correspond to the t test comparing the hidden vs salient carbon tax groups. Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals.

Fig. 2. Purchase intention by product, study, and experimental group.

P values in Study 1 correspond to the *t* test comparing the hidden vs salient carbon tax groups. Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals.

To analyze the effect of the carbon tax salience manipulation on purchase intention, controlling for different products, climate change concern, conservative political orientation, carbon tax acceptability, and perceived effectiveness as covariates, we conducted a series of multiple regression analyses. Table 1 shows the regression models predicting purchase intention with different covariates and cluster robust standard errors. We controlled for the effect of different products with product dummy variable covariates, and cell phone as the reference category. The complete multiple regression model (Model 2) significantly predicted purchase intention ($F(9, 989) = 20.84, P < 0.001, R^2 = 0.16$). All variables, except for climate change concern, and the TV and beef hamburger products covariates added significantly to explaining purchase intention. Model 1 showed that purchase intention is higher when the price increase is generated by a salient carbon tax. Compared to the purchase intention in the baseline-price control group (Figure 1), this implies that the decrease in purchase intention through the price increase is lower when the carbon tax is salient. Model 2 confirmed the robustness of this effect with climate change concern, political orientation, carbon tax acceptance, and perceived carbon tax effectiveness as covariates.

Table 1

Multiple linear regression analyses of effects on purchase intention (Study 1).

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5
Salient tax	0.31*** (0.15, 0.47)	0.36*** (0.21, 0.51)	-1.74*** (-2.25, -1.23)	1.08*** (0.81, 1.35)	-1.02* (-1.87, -0.18)
Microwave	0.49*** (0.23, 0.74)	0.47*** (0.23, 0.71)	0.49*** (0.25, 0.73)	0.47*** (0.24, 0.71)	0.49*** (0.25, 0.72)
LED TV	0.12 (-0.14, 0.37)	0.09 (-0.15, 0.34)	0.12 (-0.12, 0.35)	0.10 (-0.14, 0.33)	0.11 (-0.12, 0.35)
Beef burger	-0.16 (-0.41, 0.10)	-0.17 (-0.42, 0.08)	-0.17 (-0.42, 0.07)	-0.18 (-0.42, 0.07)	-0.18 (-0.42, 0.07)
Sports Shoes	0.51*** (0.25, 0.77)	0.49*** (0.24, 0.74)	0.49*** (0.25, 0.73)	0.48*** (0.24, 0.73)	0.49*** (0.25, 0.73)
CC concern		0.09 (-0.01, 0.19)	-0.18** (-0.30, -0.05)	0.09 (-0.01, 0.19)	-0.13 (-0.26, 0.01)
CC concern x Salient tax			0.54*** (0.41, 0.67)		0.44*** (0.28, 0.60)
Conservative		0.07* (0.01, 0.13)	0.07* (0.01, 0.13)	0.23*** (0.14, 0.31)	0.14** (0.05, 0.23)
Conservative x Salient tax				-0.31*** (-0.41, -0.21)	-0.14* (-0.26, -0.02)
CT acceptance		0.18** (0.07, 0.28)	0.17** (0.06, 0.28)	0.18** (0.07, 0.28)	0.17** (0.06, 0.28)
CT effectiveness		0.14** (0.05, 0.23)	0.13** (0.04, 0.23)	0.14** (0.05, 0.23)	0.14** (0.05, 0.23)
(Intercept)	2.36*** (2.16, 2.56)	0.76** (0.28, 1.24)	1.84*** (1.31, 2.39)	0.42 (-0.07, 0.90)	1.49*** (0.84, 2.14)
R ²	.05	.16	.21	.19	.22
N	1000	990	990	990	990

Note. *** $P < 0.001$, ** $P < 0.01$, * $P < 0.05$. Regression coefficients are unstandardized, and their 95% confidence intervals are presented in parenthesis. Robust standard errors are set at HC3. $N = 1,000$, except for models including the "conservative" variable, where 10 observations are missing because participants selected the option "I prefer not to say."

In regression models 3 and 4 we introduced the interaction effects of climate change concern and conservative political orientation, respectively, confirming the moderating influences of both variables. Model 5 confirmed the moderation by introducing both moderators together into the regression model. For participants highly concerned about climate change, carbon tax salience led to an increase in purchase intention compared to the hidden tax condition, whereas for the less

concerned this effect was not significant (Figure 3). The same pattern emerged for the influence of political orientation (Figure 4). Highly conservative individuals were not affected by the carbon tax salience effect, whereas this effect was pronounced for the less conservative. The moderating effects were significant for both climate change concern ($b_{\text{tax salience} \times \text{concern}} = 0.56$, 95% CI (0.43, 0.69), $t(992) = 8.58$, $P < 0.001$) and conservatism ($b_{\text{tax salience} \times \text{conservative}} = -0.32$, 95% CI (-0.42, -0.21), $t(982) = -5.94$, $P < 0.001$). Supplementary Note 1 of Appendix B details tax salience’s positive conditional effect on purchase intention as climate change concern increases, and its negative conditional effect as conservatism increases.

Fig. 3. The effect of carbon tax salience on purchase intention moderated by climate change concern (Study 1). *High climate change concern (+1SD) = 5.00; mean climate change concern (M) = 3.86; low climate change concern (-1SD) = 2.73. Results computed controlling for different products. Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals.*

Fig. 4. The effect of carbon tax salience on purchase intention moderated by conservative political identification (Study 1). *High conservative identification (+1SD) = 3.87; mean conservative identification (M) = 2.32; low conservative identification (-1SD) = 1.00. Results computed controlling for different products. Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals.*

The corresponding analyses for the binary variable *purchase decision* are consistent with the purchase intention results in Study 1, and are presented in Appendix B, Supplementary Note 1 (Table B.1).

5. Study 2: Moral licensing effects of salient carbon taxes

5.1. Method

5.1.1. Participants and procedure

For Study 2 we recruited a representative sample of 600 US participants (50.00% female, $M_{\text{age}} = 45.49$, $SD_{\text{age}} = 14.92$; Table A.2 in Appendix A shows demographic details) in the same way as in Study 1 through the Prolific survey platform. Participants were assigned at random to one of two

experimental groups of a between-groups experimental design (salient carbon tax vs. hidden carbon tax). The experimental manipulation of carbon tax salience was as in Study 1. The experimental shopping scenarios also replicated the method of Study 1, and exposed participants at random to either the purchase of sports shoes, a LED TV, or premium beef hamburgers. Study design, data collection method, hypotheses, and planned analyses were pre-registered on AsPredicted (<https://aspredicted.org/blind.php?x=zq6hr2>).

5.1.2. Measurement

Before rating *purchase intention* and *purchase decision* as in Study 1, to measure moral self-concept, participants were instructed to rate how they felt about purchasing the product on four five-point semantic differential scaling items (Carrico et al., 2018; Cornelissen et al., 2013; Khan and Dhar, 2006) (e.g., *guilty-virtuous*), as detailed in Table A.5. The questionnaire further measured climate change concern, carbon tax acceptability, perceived carbon tax effectiveness, political orientation, further demographic information, and the likely purpose of the survey (open-ended question) as in Study 1. None of the respondents guessed the purpose of the experiment.

5.2. Results

Participants in the salient carbon tax group reported a significantly higher moral self-concept ($M_{\text{salient}} = 3.51$, $SD_{\text{salient}} = 1.08$ vs. $M_{\text{hidden}} = 3.12$, $SD_{\text{hidden}} = 0.80$; $\Delta M = 0.38$, 95% CI (0.23, 0.53), $t(598) = 4.94$, $P < 0.001$) and purchase intention ($\Delta PI = 0.35$, 95% CI (0.14, 0.57), $t(596) = 3.19$, $P = 0.002$) than the hidden tax group, controlling for different products. There was a significant ($F(2, 594) = 3.84$, $P = 0.02$), however weak ($\eta_p^2 = 0.01$), interaction between the effects of the experimental conditions and product type on purchase intention. Regression analysis showed that the direct effect of carbon tax salience on purchase intention was positive and significant (Figure 5a) and that this effect turned non-significant when moral self-concept was introduced into the model (Figure

5b). Mediation analysis with PROCESS 3.5 (Hayes, 2017) (model 4; 10,000 bootstrap samples) provided evidence of the indirect effect of carbon tax salience on purchase intention mediated by self-concept ($b_{ind} = 0.34$, 95% Boot CI [0.21, 0.48]). These results confirm that an increase in moral self-concept explains the effect of carbon tax salience on purchase intention.

Fig. 5. The influence of carbon tax salience on purchase intention (Study 2). The relationship between tax salience and purchase intention without (a) and with (b) the mediating effect of moral self-concept. Coefficients are computed controlling for different products, climate change concern, conservative political orientation, carbon tax acceptability, and perceived effectiveness of the carbon tax. Bootstrapped 95% confidence intervals are provided in parentheses; * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$; $N = 593$ (7 observations are missing for the political orientation covariate).

The effect of carbon tax salience on moral self-concept was stronger for participants who were more concerned about climate change (Figure 6; $b_{\text{tax salience} \times \text{concern}} = 0.49$, 95% CI (0.35, 0.63), $t(594) = 6.92$, $P < 0.001$) and less conservative (Figure 7; $b_{\text{tax salience} \times \text{conservative}} = -0.29$, 95% CI (-0.39, -0.18), $t(587) = -5.38$, $P < 0.001$). The moral self-concept of the less climate-concerned and more conservative individuals was not enhanced by the salient carbon tax.

Fig. 6. Conditional effects on moral self-concept at different values of climate change concern (Study 2). *High climate change concern (+1SD) = 5.00; mean climate change concern (M) = 3.94; low climate change concern (-1SD) = 2.80. Results were adjusted for different products. N = 600. Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals.*

Fig. 7. Conditional effects on moral self-concept at different values of conservative political identification (study 2). *High conservative identification (+1SD) = 3.90; mean conservative identification (M) = 2.37; low conservative identification (-1SD) = 1.00. Results were adjusted by controlling for different products. N = 593 (7 observations are missing because some participants opted not to reveal their political orientation). Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals.*

Moderated mediation analysis (PROCESS 3.5, model 7, 10,000 bootstrap samples) (Hayes, 2017) showed that also the indirect effect of carbon tax salience on purchase intention mediated by moral self-concept was moderated by both climate change concern and conservative political orientation. Both moderators had significant moderated mediation indexes. The conditional indirect effects at different values of the moderators indicate that the mediated effect was significant for more climate-concerned and less conservative individuals, but not for the non-concerned and more conservative (Table 2). The moderated regression analysis of the main effect (i.e. without the mediation of moral self-concept) was also significant for climate change concern and conservative political orientation and is reported in Supplementary Note 2 of Appendix B. The corresponding analyses for the binary

variable *purchase decision* are consistent with the purchase intention results in Study 2, and are presented in Appendix B, Supplementary Note 2 (see Figure B.4).

Table 2

Moderated mediation analysis of the effects of carbon tax salience on demand via self-concept.

<i>Moderated mediation index</i>					
Moderator		Mod. med. index	Boot SE	Boot LLCI	Boot ULCI
Climate change concern		0.44	0.07	0.32	0.57
Conservative political orientation		-0.26	0.05	-0.35	-0.16
<i>Conditional indirect effect at values of the moderator</i>					
Moderator	Moderator values	Cond. ind. effect	Boot SE	Boot LLCI	Boot ULCI
Climate change concern	2.80 (-1SD)	-0.19	0.10	-0.37	0.01
	2.94 (M)	0.32	0.07	0.19	0.45
	5.00 (+1SD)	0.79	0.10	0.60	0.99
Conservative political orientation	1.00 (-1SD)	0.69	0.09	0.51	0.88
	2.37 (M)	0.34	0.07	0.20	0.48
	3.90 (+1SD)	-0.05	0.10	-0.25	0.15

Note. 10,000 bootstrap samples for 95% bootstrap confidence intervals, Boot SE = bootstrap (robust) standard error, Boot LLCI = bootstrap lower limit confidence interval, Boot ULCI = bootstrap upper limit confidence interval. The results are adjusted controlling for different products. The moderated mediation indexes for dependent variable *purchase decision* are expressed in log-odds metric. Values for moderators are the mean (M) and plus/minus one SD from the mean (-1SD / +1SD).

6. Study 3: Robustness of effects across different carbon tax levels

6.1. Method

6.1.1. Participants and procedure

We conducted Study 3 to assess the robustness of the carbon tax salience effect across different carbon tax levels. The US representative sample (N = 400, 51.00% female, $M_{\text{age}} = 41.66$, $SD_{\text{age}} = 15.18$; Table A.3 in Appendix A shows demographic details) was recruited in the same way as in Study 1 and Study 2. Participants were assigned at random to one of four experimental groups of a 2 (salient vs. hidden carbon tax) x 2 (low (5%) vs. high (15%) tax level) between-subjects factorial design. Carbon tax salience was manipulated as in the previous studies. Additionally, in each condition the price increases amounted to either 5% or 15% of the original price, and all participants

were presented with a shopping scenario with four products (a cell phone, a microwave oven, sports shoes, and premium beef hamburgers). A manipulation check with a different convenience sample of 100 US participants (to avoid revealing the purpose of the experiment to the participants in Study 3) confirmed that the price in the high carbon tax condition was perceived as higher than in the low tax condition (see Supplementary Note 3 of Appendix B).

6.1.2. Measurement

Participants rated, as in the previous studies, their *purchase intention* (5-point Likert scale) and *purchase decision* (binary yes/no response) for each of the products as well as their climate change concern, carbon tax acceptability, perceived effectiveness of the tax, political orientation, and demographic characteristics (see Table A.5 in Appendix A for measurement properties). A final open-ended question on the study purpose again assessed whether any participant had guessed the aim of the experiment.

6.2. Results

The effect of carbon tax salience on purchase intention was not significantly affected by the difference in carbon tax level ($b_{\text{Tax salience} \times \text{Tax level}} = 0.23$, 95% CI (-0.05, 0.50), $t(1596) = 1.64$, $P = 0.101$; that is, the carbon tax salience effect was not significantly moderated by the amount of the price rise (low: 5% vs. high: 15%). Purchase intention increased similarly for the salient vs. hidden carbon tax when the tax level was either low ($\Delta PI_{\text{low}} = 0.54$, 95% CI (0.35, 0.74), $t(795) = 5.46$, $P < 0.001$) or high ($\Delta PI_{\text{high}} = 0.77$, 95% CI (0.58, 0.96), $t(795) = 8.11$, $P < 0.001$). There was no evidence of an interaction between the effects of the experimental conditions and product type on purchase intention ($F(3, 1592) = 1.37$, $P = 0.25$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.01$).

As detailed in Supplementary Note 3 of Appendix B, we ran six multiple regression models for the purchase intention (Table B.3) and the purchase decision variables (Table B.4), adding controls

and moderators. As in previous studies, purchase decision results were consistent with the results obtained with the purchase intention variable. Since the dataset contained repeated observations per participant (i.e., all products were rated by all participants), the regression parameters were estimated with cluster-robust standard errors to account for the nested data.

In addition, the study replicated the moderating effects of climate change concern and political orientation. Climate change concern significantly moderated the effect of carbon tax salience on purchase intention ($b_{\text{tax salience} \times \text{concern}} = 0.31$, 95% CI (0.20, 0.43), $t(1593) = 5.27$, $P < 0.001$). Highly concerned individuals increased their consumption when the tax was salient while non-concerned participants were unaffected by the salience effect (Figure B.9). The carbon tax salience effect on purchase intention was also moderated by conservative political orientation ($b_{\text{tax salience} \times \text{conservative}} = -0.22$, 95% CI (-0.31, -0.13), $t(1593) = -4.67$, $P < 0.001$), with less conservative participants significantly increasing their purchase intention when they were aware that a carbon tax was included in the price (Figure B.10). Both moderation analyses used cluster robust standard errors and controlled for the carbon tax level and different products. Supplementary Note 3 of Appendix B details tax salience's positive conditional effect on purchase intention as climate change concern increases, and its negative conditional effect as conservatism increases.

7. Study 4: Alternative explanations and carbon label

7.1. Method

7.1.1. Participants and procedure

Study 4 replicated the carbon tax salience effect in a simulated online shopping environment presenting product pictures and detailed product information. The study had the further objectives to test whether the carbon tax salience effect was affected by carbon footprint information (carbon label) and to rule out the alternative explanation that it was driven by participants understanding the carbon tax as a signal of a higher environmentally friendliness of the product. The US representative

sample ($N = 400$, 50.00% female, $M_{\text{age}} = 44.07$, $SD_{\text{age}} = 14.29$; Table A.4 in Appendix A shows demographic details) was recruited in the same way as in the previous studies. Participants were assigned at random to one of four experimental groups of a 2 (salient vs. hidden carbon tax) x 2 (carbon label vs. control) between-subjects factorial design. Carbon tax salience was manipulated as in the previous studies. All participants were presented with three products (a microwave oven, sports shoes, and a LED TV) and asked to rate their purchase intention. The purchase scenarios simulated an online shopping environment, detailing product information and providing screenshots of a mock-up Amazon-inspired webpage (see *Experimental Survey Materials* in Appendix A). For participants in the carbon label condition, each product was presented with an additional carbon label that provided carbon footprint information (carbon emissions during manufacturing and distribution). The carbon label manipulation aimed to assess whether the carbon tax salience effect would remain stable in presence of further carbon footprint information.

7.1.2. Measurement

After assessing their purchase intention (5-point Likert scale) and purchase decision (binary yes/no response) for all products, participants were asked to rate the *environmental friendliness* of each product using a 5-point Likert scale (Hartmann and Apaolaza-Ibáñez, 2012; Whitmarsh et al., 2011) (Table A.5). We measured this variable after the purchase intention for all products had been rated to rule out prompting environmental thoughts during the simulated purchases other than those evoked by the carbon tax and carbon label manipulation. The aim of measuring environmental friendliness was to address the alternative explanation that carbon tax salience could enhance the perceived environmental friendliness of the product and contribute in this way to increasing purchase likelihood. As in the remaining studies, participants indicated, in this order, their climate change concern, carbon tax acceptance, perceived effectiveness of the tax, political orientation, and

demographic characteristics. These scales were measured as in the previous studies (see Table A.5 in Appendix A for measurement properties).

7.2. Results

Study 4 again showed that purchase intention was higher when the carbon tax was salient instead of hidden ($\Delta PI = 0.33$, 95% CI (0.18, 0.48), $t(1195) = 4.40$, $P < 0.001$). Providing carbon footprint information did neither affect the perception of the products' environmental friendliness ($\Delta M = 0.04$, 95% CI (-0.18, 0.25), $t(398) = 0.32$, $P = 0.751$) nor purchase intention ($\Delta PI = -0.04$, 95% CI (-0.19, 0.11), $t(1198) = -0.55$, $P = 0.586$). The carbon tax salience effect did not interact with the presence of a carbon label in the product ($b_{\text{Tax salience} \times \text{Carbon label}} = -0.06$, 95% CI (-0.35, 0.24), $t(1194) = 0.71$, $P = 0.705$). There were no significant differences in purchase intention between the participants exposed to the salient carbon tax with the product's carbon footprint information and those exposed to the salient carbon tax alone.

Indicating the carbon tax as part of the product's price did also not significantly increase the perception of its environmental friendliness ($\Delta M = 0.14$, 95% CI (-0.08, 0.36), $t(398) = 1.27$, $P = 0.205$). There is therefore no evidence supporting that the increase in purchase intention triggered by carbon tax salience could be attributed to an increase in the perceived environmental friendliness of the product. There was also no evidence of an interaction between the effects of the experimental conditions and product type on purchase intention ($F(2, 1194) = 0.37$, $P = 0.69$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.01$).

As detailed in Supplementary Note 4 of Appendix B, we ran five multiple regression models for the purchase intention (Table B.5) and the purchase decision variables (Table B.6), adding controls and moderators. Purchase decision results were again consistent with the results obtained for purchase intention. The regression parameters were also estimated with cluster-robust standard errors to account for the nested data.

Climate change concern again significantly moderated the effect of carbon tax salience on purchase intention ($b_{\text{tax salience} \times \text{concern}} = 0.25$, 95% CI (0.12, 0.38), $t(1193) = 3.66$, $P = 0.003$). Highly concerned individuals increased their consumption when the tax was salient while non-concerned participants were unaffected by the salience effect (Figure B.13). The carbon tax salience effect on purchase intention was also moderated by conservative political orientation ($b_{\text{tax salience} \times \text{conservative}} = -0.12$, 95% CI (-0.22, -0.02), $t(1193) = -2.43$, $P = 0.015$) (Figure B.14). Both moderation analyses used cluster robust standard errors and controlled for the carbon label and different products. Supplementary Note 4 of Appendix B details tax salience’s positive conditional effect on purchase intention as climate change concern increases, and its negative conditional effect as conservatism increases.

8. Internal meta-analysis

Our studies provided consistent evidence that a carbon tax reduces demand for consumer products to a lesser extent (up to not reducing it at all) when the tax is shown as part of the product price (Table 3). Individually, all our studies delivered significant effect sizes (Cohen’s d) for the purchase intention variables.

Table 3

Purchase intention (PI) means and mean differences (ΔPI) across studies and conditions.

Study	PI hidden tax	PI salient tax	ΔPI	P -value	Cohen's d
Study 1	2.55 (2.44, 2.66)	2.85 (2.73, 2.98)	0.31 (0.14, 0.47)	< 0.001	0.23 (0.10, 0.35)
Study 2	2.70 (2.55, 2.85)	3.05 (2.89, 3.21)	0.35 (0.11, 0.57)	< 0.001	0.25 (0.09, 0.42)
Study 3	2.68 (2.59, 2.78)	3.34 (3.24, 3.43)	0.66 (0.52, 0.79)	< 0.001	0.48 (0.38, 0.58)
Study 4	2.53 (2.42, 2.63)	2.86 (2.75, 2.96)	0.33 (0.18, 0.48)	< 0.001	0.25 (0.14, 0.36)

Note. P -values test for the difference between hidden and salient carbon tax experimental groups. Effects size (Cohen’s d) provides a standardized metric of the magnitude of differences between conditions. 95% confidence intervals are provided in parentheses. Results were computed controlling for different products.

We conducted an internal meta-analysis to combine the effect sizes from all our studies into a single estimate. To account for heterogeneity across studies, we conducted a random effect analysis, that weighted effect sizes. We chose the random effects over a fixed-effects model because the former accommodates possible unequal variability in effect sizes (i.e., heterogeneity). A potential source of heterogeneity across studies was that we used different combinations of products. The carbon tax salience effect was overall supported by the internal meta-analysis over the four main studies and all products (random effects; $d_+ = 0.31$, 95% CI (0.19, 0.43), $z = 4.96$, $P < 0.001$, $Q(3) = 13.51$, $I^2 = 74.93\%$), as well as for each product over the four main studies (see Supplementary Note 6 of Appendix B).

We additionally conducted five internal meta-analyses (one per product) to obtain the overall effect size for each product individually across studies. In this case, we used fixed-effects models because each product was analyzed individually. Table B.8 shows that salient carbon taxes consistently increased purchase likelihood for each product individually.

9. Discussion and implications

9.1. Findings and theoretical contribution

9.1.1. Consumer demand effects of carbon tax salience

The primary aim of carbon taxes is to reduce climate harmful carbon-intensive consumption. However, as our studies show, a salient carbon tax of which consumers are aware may not achieve the desired outcome. Our four experimental studies and two pilot studies with different products, prices, carbon tax levels, and purchasing scenarios provided consistent evidence that, as a consequence of moral licensing, salient carbon taxes indicated as part of the product price are less effective in curbing demand than hidden ones. Results remained robust when controlling for climate change concern, political identification, environmental perception of the product, carbon tax acceptance, and perceived carbon tax effectiveness. This effect was also not significantly affected by

differences in the carbon tax level (5% vs. 15%). In all studies, the influence of carbon tax salience was more pronounced for more climate-concerned and less conservative participants. The overall effect of carbon tax salience on purchase intention, indicated by our internal meta-analysis over the four main studies and all products (Cohen's $d = 0.31$, 95% CI (0.19, 0.43)), matched the average magnitude of moral licensing effects (Cohen's $d = 0.31$, 95% CI (0.23, 0.38)) estimated by Blanken et al. (2015) in their meta-analysis of the moral licensing literature.

The effect of salient vs. hidden carbon taxes had not been addressed in prior research. Our findings add novel insight to the current debate on the effectiveness of carbon pricing and incentives (Hahnel et al., 2020; Lanz et al., 2018; Rivers and Schaufele, 2015; Soregaroli et al., 2021) by showing that a price increase leads to a smaller decrease in demand when consumers are aware that it was caused by a carbon tax. Our results support the view that being aware of paying a carbon tax can alter consumers' purchase behavior, for instance by changing endogenous preferences (Hahnel et al., 2020; Mattauch et al., 2022; Panzone et al., 2021), but are contrary to the prior finding that a visible carbon tax on gasoline can have a stronger demand curbing influence than market-driven price increases (Rivers and Schaufele, 2015). While monetary incentives designed to switch to grocery products with a lower carbon footprint are less effective than neutrally framed price decreases of the same magnitude (Lanz et al., 2018), our study showed a similar pattern for the case of price increases: a higher price caused by a visible carbon tax was less effective in reducing demand than the same price without carbon tax information.

9.1.2. Carbon tax salience triggers moral licensing

Study 2 provided evidence that the effect of salient vs. hidden carbon taxes is the result of a moral licensing process triggered by the anticipation of paying the tax. Consumers perceive that paying the carbon tax as part of the product price is a moral act that licenses the purchase and consumption of the product, despite carbon emissions. The effect of carbon tax salience on purchase intention can be

explained by an increase in moral self-concept, confirming moral licensing. Paying the carbon tax reduces consumers' guilt concerning their carbon footprint and boosts their moral self-concept. Study 4 did not provide evidence for the alternative explanation that this effect was driven by participants understanding the carbon tax as a signal of a higher environmentally friendliness of the product. There is therefore no evidence supporting that the increase in purchase intention triggered by carbon tax salience could be attributed to an increase in the perceived environmental friendliness of the product.

These findings contribute to moral licensing theory and research (e.g., Jordan et al., 2011; Merritt et al., 2010; Monin and Miller, 2001; Mullen and Monin, 2016), and its application to environmental behavior (Burger et al., 2022; Meijers et al., 2014; Noblet and McCoy, 2018; Werfel, 2017) by showing that moral licensing can play a significant role in consumer decisions regarding their carbon footprint, and, specifically, as a response to carbon taxes. Our results provide novel insight since there has been no prior research connecting moral licensing to the effects of carbon taxing. In particular, we show that paying a carbon tax can be construed by the individual as a moral behavior that, as argued by moral licensing theory (Blanken et al., 2015; Khan and Dhar, 2006), can boost an individual's moral self-image to the extent that they are subsequently more likely to act immorally. Our findings furthermore support Stoll and Mehling's (2021) view that consumers may not react as modeled to carbon pricing policies because psychological mechanisms triggered by the monetary incentive will disrupt the price signal, and shows that moral licensing can be such a mechanism.

9.1.3. Carbon tax licensing is stronger for the environmentally concerned and less conservative

In all four studies, the moral licensing effect of salient carbon taxes was more pronounced for individuals who were more environmentally concerned and identified themselves as less conservative. Compared to the same price increase caused by a hidden carbon tax, a salient carbon tax was more likely to increase participants' purchase intention if they were highly concerned about

climate change. Conversely, the carbon tax salience effect was not significant for the less concerned participants. A similar pattern emerged for the influence of political orientation: Highly conservative individuals were not affected by the carbon tax salience effect, whereas this effect was pronounced for the less conservative. The moderating influences of climate change concern and political orientation were replicated in all four studies. These findings contribute to the literature on the effectiveness of carbon pricing and incentives (Hahnel et al., 2020; Lanz et al., 2018; Rivers and Schaufele, 2015; Soregaroli et al., 2021) by providing additional boundary conditions that may have rather counterintuitive influences: carbon tax effectiveness may be reduced exactly for those consumers—the climate concerned and less conservative—that are most likely to support carbon taxes and their demand-reducing effects. Our results also provide an additional perspective to Alcock et al. (2017), who found that pro-environmental attitudes are only related to some pro-environmental behaviors (household behaviors) but not to others (air travel) and that low carbon household behavior does not positively spill over to air travel. Study 2 furthermore provided evidence that the moderation of the carbon tax salience effect by climate concern and political orientation can be explained by the moderating influence of these variables on the moral licensing process. The effect of carbon tax salience on moral self-concept was stronger for participants who were more concerned about climate change and rated themselves as less conservative.

This finding adds environmental concern and political orientation as novel moderators to the theory explaining when and when not prior moral behavior will lead to moral licensing (Mullen and Monin, 2016) and supports the hypothesis that individuals are more prone to moral licensing the stronger they are committed to the behavior that provides them with the moral credential to license (Burger et al., 2022; Gholamzadehmir et al., 2019), in this case, reducing their carbon footprint to mitigate climate change. Our results seem to be at odds with empirical findings showing that identity-relevant issues and environmental concern prevent moral licensing behavior (e.g. Maki et al., 2019; Noblet and McCoy, 2018). But the importance attributed to the initial behavior can also

serve as a cognitive dissonance-reducing strategy (Starzyk et al., 2009): Strongly concerned individuals are more likely to resort to moral licensing when they have to divert their attention from the psychological discomfort of making a new pro-environmental decision (Burger et al., 2022; Gholamzadehmira et al., 2019). In the same situation, the moral permission to license will be less obvious to non-concerned individuals because they might not consider paying the carbon tax as a moral act.

9.2. Practical implications

Retailers can exploit this moral licensing effect to neutralize carbon pricing by making the carbon tax salient as part of the retail price. To prevent a decreased effectiveness of carbon prices due to consumers' awareness of the tax included in the product price, policymakers could prohibit indicating the carbon tax amount in retail prices. However, a lack of transparency could jeopardize the political acceptability of carbon taxes (Klenert et al., 2018; Maestre-Andrés et al., 2021, 2019). Conversely, if carbon taxes are made salient to avoid public opposition, the measure could be less effective. Still, the target-compatible carbon price could be adjusted upwards to account for consumers' biased reactions (Farhi and Gabaix, 2020; Huse, 2018; Mattauch et al., 2022). A climate-target-compatible carbon price of \$40-\$50 per ton of carbon emissions (Carbon Pricing Leadership Coalition, 2017) would raise production costs between 1% and 7%, depending on the industry (Gray and Metcalf, 2017; Nakano and Yamagishi, 2021). Yet, the average US household could be willing to assume price increases of up to 14.4% in their energy bill if it was caused by a carbon tax (Kotchen et al., 2017). Based on these estimates, in Study 3 we tested the effects of 5% and 15% price increases on consumer demand. Results showed that the effect of carbon tax salience on purchase intention was not significantly affected by the difference in carbon tax level. Although a much higher carbon tax will eventually outweigh the carbon tax salience effect, a significantly higher carbon price seems at present unfeasible given the current carbon pricing trajectories (Carbon Pricing

Leadership Coalition, 2017), which face downward pressure due to public and political opposition (Carattini et al., 2017; Jenkins, 2014).

10. Limitations and future research

Our findings need to be taken with some caution, as the studies were not conducted in real purchase scenarios. Still, we deemed the use of survey experiments in a controlled setting appropriate because the primary objective of our research was to obtain robust evidence of consumer responses to carbon tax salience and the psychological mechanism underpinning this effect. Nevertheless, our findings should be replicated in a field experiment using longitudinal data to determine the extent to which the carbon tax salient effect encourages consumption in real-world purchase scenarios. Meta-analytic evidence from previous behavioral spillover studies in the environmental domain warns that changes in actual behavior (e.g., spending own money on a purchase) are not as strong as the behavioral intentions (e.g., a costless purchase intention claim) reported by survey participants (Maki et al., 2019). Our experiments could have overestimated the impact of the salient carbon tax, as participants did not have to pay for the products. Moreover, the moral licensing effect generated by carbon tax salience might not be as consistent as observed in the present research because in real purchase scenarios (e.g., grocery shopping in crowded supermarkets) consumers have limited cognitive resources and resort to mental shortcuts. Another potential limitation of our studies is that we informed participants that the carbon tax was a measure introduced to “lower the carbon emissions generated during the manufacturing and transport of all products.” Our studies did not address whether the observed effect of salient vs. hidden carbon taxes would materialize within a purchase scenario that did not establish a relationship between the carbon tax and overall emissions reductions. Participants may have interpreted the carbon tax as a carbon offset mechanism for the product they purchased, even if we did not state this in the purchase scenario. Such a perception may have contributed to the increase in moral self-concept or triggered

an alternative effect on purchase intention, based on carbon offsetting. Future experiments should test the observed effects without providing information on the aims and scope of the carbon tax to participants.

Further research is also needed to explore which heuristics exacerbate and attenuate moral licensing. For instance, under partisan affective polarization (Iyengar and Westwood, 2015) purchase decisions can be made heuristically according to identity-expressive functions which could lead democrat-leaning individuals to believe that consuming carbon-taxed products is socially desirable because it signals their partisan support. Also, consumers who are informed about the use of carbon tax revenues to reduce carbon emissions may feel less morally accountable for the environmental impact of their purchase decisions. Such *green earmarking* is an effective policy design to reduce public opposition (Klenert et al., 2018; Maestre-Andrés et al., 2019). We anticipate a promising research avenue in this regard: Carbon tax designs that maximize policy acceptability, like salient taxes with green revenue earmarking, may also have the highest likelihood of triggering moral licensing processes.

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